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SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D3.2- EPORT AND DATABASE OF CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF DIFFERENT AGRICULTURAL FIELDS ACROSS

Universida de Vigo

D3.2. REPORT AND DATABASE OF CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF DIFFERENT AGRICULTURAL FIELDS ACROSS THE MAJOR EUROPEAN PEDOCLIMATIC REGIONS

Summary

One of the main objectives of the WP3 is to assess the relationship between soil biodiversity and soil properties along different European Pedoclimatic regions in conventional and organic wheat field. For this purpose, an exhaustive analysis of 188 soils from 9 pedoclimatic regions was performed. In addition wheat characteristics were also analyzed.

This deliverable presents, in the form of Tables and statistical analyses, results of the following soil:

- Soil field moisture content.
- Soil bulk density
- Soil aggregate size distribution.
- Soil aggregates mean weight diameter.
- Soil rock fragments and gravels.
- Soil particle size distribution
- Soil pH.
- Soil cation exchange capacity
- Soil electrical conductivity
- Soil organic matter content, total organic carbon, particulate organic carbon and carbonates content
- Soil total nitrogen and nitrogen forms
- Soil macronutrients (P, K, Ca and Mg)
- Soil micronutrients (Cu, Fe, Mn and Zn)
- Pesticide residues in soils

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1 Introduction

During a sampling campaign, soil samples were taken to determine the current status of biodiversity across 9 European pedoclimatic regions (see Deliverable 3.3). These results will be used as a reference or baseline for the establishment of soil biodiversity targets for sustainable agricultural soil management. However, agricultural systems differ extensively across Europe and the recognition of these systems is essential to define regional development programs towards a more sustainable European agriculture. Different agricultural systems developed because of historical events and local legislation, but more importantly because of different climatic conditions and soil characteristics across Europe. In contrast to above ground biodiversity, underground biodiversity is only limitedly shaped by climatological conditions, far more important is the soil itself due to a direct and intimate contact with soil particles and a number of soluble and insoluble substances present.

The soil organisms' development and activity largely depends on the condition and composition of its environment, in this case the soil. Therefore, work package 3 of the SoildiverAgro-project includes the investigation of a large set of physical and chemical soil characteristics (Deliverable 3.2) to not only relate the obtained biodiversity results (Deliverable 3.3) to climate conditions and the agricultural management system, but also to relate it to soil properties (Deliverable 3.4).

This report documents on results obtained concerning Deliverable 3.2. In 9 pedoclimatic regions, at least 10 farms of which 5 following a conventional and 5 following an organic way of farming, were selected for soil sampling. Almost exclusively wheat fields were sampled shortly after harvest to ensure comparable conditions between the regions regarding the agricultural system and its activities. To further ensure that variation due to different technical approaches and operators interferes with sample variation, one laboratory was selected to process all soil samples to obtain a set of physical and chemical soil properties.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Soil and wheat sampling

Soil samples were collected from nine European pedoclimatic regions at different countries (Table 1), i.e., Atlantic North (AN), Atlantic Central (AC), Boreal (BOR), Continental (CON), Lusitanian (LUS), Mediterranean North (MN), Mediterranean South (MS), Nemoral (NEM) and Pannonian (PAN). A map of all pedoclimatic regions studied can be consulted at Figure 1. Soil samples were collected in wheat plots with organic and conventional management 15-30 d after the wheat harvesting. The number of plots per management type is shown at Table 1.

Fig 1. European pedoclimatic regions included in SoildiverAgro

Table 1. Number of sampled plots at each pedoclimatic region and their corresponding countries

Table 1		
Pedoclimatic region	Country	Plots per management type
AN	Denmark	10 (O), 10 (C)
AC	Belgium	12 (O), 13 (C)
BOR	Finland	10 (O), 10 (C)
CON	Germany	10 (O), 10 (C)
LUS	Spain	13 (O), 10 (C)
MN	Spain	10 (O), 10 (C)
MS	Spain	10 (O), 10 (C)
NEM	Estonia	10 (O), 10 (C)
PAN	Serbia and Hungary	10 (O), 10 (C)

“O” and “C” corresponds to organic and conventional management, respectively.

Different soil sampling was carried out per plot separately attending the different analysis: i) a composite sample (2 kg minimum) was collected at 0-25 cm depth at around 60 random representative points per plot using a sampler probe. This type of sample was homogenized and split into two parts: one part was sieved by a 2 mm mesh in fresh, and the other part was dried at room temperature. The dry soil was separated again into two parts: around 100 g of dry soil was used to measure the aggregate size distribution and the aggregates mean weight diameter (AMWD) and the rest was sieved by 2-mm mesh to perform physicochemical analysis; ii) three soil samples per plot were collected to measure bulk density (BD). A scheme of the sampling procedure is shown at Fernández-Calviño et al. (2020).

2.2 Soil analyses

Initially, field moisture content (F_{Ma}) was measured in fresh soil after weighting an aliquot of wet soil and putting the sample in the oven at 105 °C until constant weight (minimum of 10 h). After that, dried sample was weighted again and F_{Ma} was calculated by difference between wet and dry soil divided by wet soil mass, i.e., it means the water content of a soil sample at sampling time, expressed as percentage.

Bulk density (undisturbed soil) was measured by the gravimetric method. These samples were collected using metal cores to measure at two different depths, i.e., 0-10 and 10-25 cm.

Aggregate size distribution and the aggregates mean weight diameter (dry and unsieved soil) were measured following the wet sieving method. Aggregate size distribution was separated into different fractions: >2000 µm, 250-2000 µm, 53-250 µm and <53 µm.

Physicochemical analysis of wet and sieved soil samples included NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ determination which were analyzed in a soil extract KCl 2M according to Sempere et al. (1993), Kandeler and Gerber (1988) and Keeny and Nelson (1982) by ion chromatography (nitrate and nitrite) and spectrophotometry (ammonium).

The rest of physicochemical parameters were determined in the dry and sieved soil:

Particle size distribution (PSD) and texture were determined by the pipette method. The PSD includes the determination of gravels content (>2 mm) by using a 2-mm sieve and mineral particles smaller than 2 mm by sieving and sedimentation obtaining the following fractions: sand (2-0.05 mm), silt (0.05-0.002 mm) and clay (<0.002 mm).

pH in water (pH_w) and in saline solutions, i.e., KCl (pH_k) and CaCl₂ (pH_c), were measured with a glass electrode in a soil suspension (1:5 soil:solution ratio) using distilled water, 1M of KCl and 0.01M CaCl₂, respectively.

Organic matter (OM) was determined following the loss-on-ignition (LOI) method. For that, a soil sample is burnt in a muffle at 450°C for 4 h (LOI). OM is obtained by weighting the difference before and after burning the soil. After this, the carbon in the burnt sample is determined by an Elemental Analyzer obtaining the total inorganic carbon (TIC). On the other

side, total carbon (TC) and total nitrogen (Nt) are also determined in grinded sample by an Elemental Analyzer. Then, the total organic carbon (TOC) will be obtained by difference between TC and TIC. Additionally, particulate organic carbon (POC) was also determined. It was measured based on the soil physical fractionation to distinguish specific soil carbon pools. The procedure consists of dispersing the sample and then sieve it through 0.053 mm mesh. The fraction retained on the sieve, i.e., fraction size >0.053 mm is C- and N-analyzed in an Elemental Analyzer as the POC.

The determination of exchangeable Ca (Ca_{ex}), exchangeable K (K_{ex}), exchangeable Mg (Mg_{ex}), exchangeable Na (Na_{ex}), sum of bases (Bs) and effective cation exchange capacity (CEC) was performed following the ISO 2018 standard.

Available phosphorus (P_{av}) was obtained according to the Olsen method.

Bioavailable Cu, Zn, Fe and Mn (Cu_{ba} , Zn_{ba} , Fe_{ba} and Mn_{ba} , respectively) were obtained using DTPA extractant.

More details of each method used can be found at Fernández-Calviño et al. (2020)

To measure multi-pesticides residues, we use the QUECHERS method (Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, and Safe), based on an European Standard (EN 15662:2018) for the determination of pesticide residues on foods of plant origin, and adapted to measure soil samples (Mol et al. 2008; Silva et al. 2019). This method is based on pesticide extraction with one or several solvents, the cleaning of the sample to avoid interferences and the determination of pesticides by LC-MS/MS and GC-HRMS. The quantification limit was 0.005 mg kg^{-1} .

Given the importance of glyphosate and AMPA, these two substances are usually extracted by using more specific methods, that will be explained in detail in the following section. To measure glyphosate, glufosinate ammonium and their metabolites (AMPA for Glyphosate, MPP and n-Acetyl-glufosinate for Glufosinate ammonium), we use the QuPPE-PO-Method for analysis of highly polar pesticides in food involving extraction with acidified methanol and adapted to measure soil samples (EURL 2021). Determination was carried out by UPLC-MS/MS. The quantification limit was 0.01 mg kg^{-1} (0.05 mg kg^{-1} for MPP).

2.3 Statistics

Data normality was checked using Kolmogorov-Smirnov when $n \geq 30$, and Shapiro-Wilk when $n < 30$. The homogeneity of variance was tested using Levene's test. When data were normally distributed, the statistical significance of differences between region and management were estimated using one-way ANOVA, for equal (Bonferroni posthoc test) and no equal variances (Games-Howell posthoc test, which is robust to heteroscedasticity). When data were not normally distributed, we tried to normalize them using log or square root transformations. When transformations did not work, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used for non-normally distributed data expressing equal variance. Based on statistics recommendations, one-way

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ANOVA followed by the Games- Howell posthoc test was used in one particularly challenging case even though data were not normal, and variance was not equal. The statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS statistics 25.0. Results which show different letters mean significant differences among each parameter.

3 Results

Results obtained for each soil or wheat sample will be available at Zenodo repository at SoildiverAgro Community.

3.1 Soil analyses

3.1.1 Field soil moisture content (FMa)

Field soil moisture ranged from 3 to 40% considering all studied soils. Lower FMa values were found at Mediterranean regions, both in the North (MN) and in the South (MS), while higher FMa were found as an average at Boreal region (BOR). General gradient is $BOR^a > CON^b \geq AN^{bc} \approx AC^{bc} \approx NEM^{bc} \geq PAN^c \geq LUS^{cd} \geq MN^{de} \geq MS^e$. Therefore, there is a clear variation from North to South. Average and range data per region considering the two types of management are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Soil bulk density (BD) measured at 0-10 and 10-25 cm and actual field moisture (FMa) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 2													
Pedoclimatic region	Management	BD (0-10) [g/cm ³]				BD (10-25) [g/cm ³]				FMa [%]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	1.4	0.1	1.5	1.2	1.4	0.1	1.5	1.3	15.4	2.8	19.7	8.5
	Org	1.4	0.1	1.5	1.2	1.4	0.1	1.5	1.2	13.9	4.6	26.8	9.0
AN	Conv	0.9	0.2	1.4	0.7	1.3	0.3	1.6	0.8	16.4	5.3	23.6	9.2
	Org	1.2	0.2	1.4	0.8	1.3	0.2	1.6	0.9	16.7	3.1	21.0	11.2
BOR	Conv	1.0	0.1	1.2	0.9	1.2	0.1	1.3	1.1	25.7	3.6	33.4	21.3
	Org	1.1	0.1	1.3	0.7	1.1	0.2	1.3	0.8	25.3	6.7	39.8	14.3
CON	Conv	1.2	0.1	1.4	1.0	1.4	0.2	1.7	1.1	17.7	3.0	20.8	12.5
	Org	1.2	0.2	1.4	0.9	1.2	0.1	1.4	1.1	17.2	4.2	22.4	9.2
LUS	Conv	1.3	0.1	1.4	1.1	1.4	0.1	1.5	1.3	10.0	3.5	14.9	3.0
	Org	1.0	0.2	1.4	0.8	1.2	0.2	1.5	0.9	14.3	9.2	36.3	4.4
MN	Conv	1.1	0.2	1.5	0.8	NA	NA	NA	NA	9.7	2.7	12.7	5.2
	Org	1.3	0.1	1.5	1.2	NA	NA	NA	NA	4.9	1.0	7.1	3.4
MS	Conv	1.1	0.1	1.2	1.0	NA	NA	NA	NA	7.5	3.1	15.6	4.5
	Org	1.3	0.1	1.4	1.1	NA	NA	NA	NA	5.6	1.6	8.0	3.1
NEM	Conv	1.2	0.2	1.5	1.0	1.4	0.1	1.6	1.2	15.0	1.7	16.7	10.8
	Org	1.1	0.1	1.3	1.0	1.2	0.1	1.3	1.0	14.2	5.1	23.2	8.7
PAN	Conv	NA	NA	NA	NA	1.4	0.1	1.7	1.2	13.2	2.3	17.3	10.2
	Org	NA	NA	NA	NA	1.4	0.1	1.6	1.2	13.3	2.6	16.1	9.5

NA: not available data.

As regards to the soil management, no significant differences were found between conventional and organic agricultural practices considering all obtained data ($t = 0.604$, $P > 0.05$). However, analysing each region separately, significant differences were only found at MN between managements ($t = 5.52$; $P < 0.001$). Therefore, soil moisture after wheat sampling was clearly more influenced by sampling area than type of management.

3.1.2 Soil bulk density (BD)

Soil bulk density ranged between 0.7-1.5 g/cm³ up to 10 cm depth among all soils, resulting in the following ranking: $AC^a \geq MN^{ab} \geq MS^b \approx CON^b \approx NEM^b \approx LUS^b \approx BOR^b \approx AN^b$. Data from PAN region were not available (NA). Results also show that there are no significant differences between management practices when analysing all data together. Average and range BD per region considering the two types of management are shown in Table 2. By analysing each region separately, there were significant differences between conventional and organic management in AN ($Z = -2.307$, $P < 0.05$), LUS ($t = 4.612$, $P < 0.001$), MN ($t = -3.586$, $P < 0.05$), MS ($t = -4.033$, $P < 0.05$).

Soil BD from 10 to 25 cm depth varied between 0.8-1.7 g/cm³ comparing all data. The resulted ranking is $AC^a \geq PAN^{ab} \approx AN^{ab} \approx CON^{ab} \geq LUS^b \approx NEM^b \approx BOR^b$. The management practices did not provide significant differences for BD from 10 to 25 cm. Data from MN and MS regions were not available (NA). Average and range BD per region considering the two types of management are shown in Table 2. Performing regional analysis, conventional management was significantly different from organic at CON ($t = 2.24$, $P < 0.05$), LUS ($t = 3.377$, $P < 0.05$) and NEM ($t = 3.027$, $P < 0.05$).

The results show that there were no clear differences in BD among regions. Moreover, the effect of management may present some effect on BD, but only in some regions.

3.1.3 Soil aggregate size distribution (Agsd)

Soil aggregate size distribution was separated into four fractions and each one is expressed as percentage of the total sample: $>2000 \mu\text{m}$ (agsd_b), $250-2000 \mu\text{m}$ (agsd_c), $53-250 \mu\text{m}$ (agsd_d) and $<53 \mu\text{m}$ (agsd_e). Agsd_b, c, d and e ranged between 0-60%, 4-76%, 8-75% and 2-65%, respectively among all soils. Considering each region, the ranking for agsd_b resulted in $MN^a > BOR^{ab} \geq AN^b \approx AC^b \geq LUS^{bc} \approx MS^{bc} \approx NEM^{bc} \approx CON^{bc} \geq PAN^c$; for agsd_c, the ranking resulted in $LUS^a \geq AC^{ab} \approx AN^{ab} \geq BOR^b \geq NEM^{bc} \geq CON^c \approx MN^c \approx PAN^c \approx MS^c$. For agsd_d, the ranking resulted in $PAN^a \approx MS^a \approx NEM^a > CON^b \approx AN^b \geq MN^{bc} \approx AC^{bc} \geq LUS^c > BOR^d$. And, for agsd_e, the ranking resulted in $PAN^a \approx CON^a \approx MS^a \geq BOR^{ab} \geq AC^b \approx MN^b \approx NEM^b \approx LUS^b \approx AN^b$. Average and range data per region considering the two types of management per each fraction are shown in Table 3. Performing analysis per region, conventional was significantly different from organic management regarding the parameter Agsd_b at AC ($Z = -2.448$, $P < 0.05$), AN ($t = 2.539$, $P < 0.05$), LUS ($t = 4.149$, $P < 0.005$) and MS ($t = 3.6$, $P < 0.01$) regions; regarding Agsd_c, at AC ($t = 9.774$, $P < 0.001$), LUS ($t = -2.448$, $P < 0.05$), MN ($Z = -2.117$, $P < 0.05$), MS

($t = -2.71$, $P < 0.05$), PAN ($t = -3.544$, $P < 0.01$) were found significant differences between conventional and organic management; in the case of Agsd_d, only at AC ($t = -5.186$, $P < 0.001$) and AN ($t = -3.302$, $P < 0.01$) regions were found significant differences between conventional and organic management; for Agsd_e only at MS were found significant differences ($t = 6.132$, $P < 0.001$) between both managements. It should be noted that no trends can be established for aggregate size distribution parameter.

3.1.4 Aggregates mean weight diameter (AMWD)

This parameter provides information about the mean size of aggregates from undisturbed soil, i.e., about the structural status of soil based on macro-aggregates stability. AMWD values ranged between 0.2 – 3.3 mm among all studied soils. Performing the analysis per region, the obtained ranking was $MN^a \geq BOR^{ab} \approx AN^{ab} \geq AC^b \approx LUS^b \geq NEM^{bc} \geq CON^c \approx MS^c \approx PAN^c$. Average and range data per region considering the two types of management per each fraction are shown in Table 3. Average and range data per region considering the two types of management are shown in Table 3. Considering each region separately, management type it was significantly different at AC ($t = 2.805$, $P < 0.05$), LUS ($t = 5.237$, $P < 0.001$), MS ($t = -4.319$, $P < 0.01$) and PAN ($t = -4.272$, $P < 0.001$).

3.1.5 Rock fragments and gravels (Rfg) and particle size distribution of soil fraction < 2 mm

Particle size distribution, including rock fragments and gravels (Rfg), sand (SA) 2-0.05 mm, silt (SI) 0.05-0.002 mm and clay (CL) <0.002 mm determine the structure and composition of soils. Rfg ranged between 0.1-64% of the total sample collected while SA, SI and CL ranged between 9-76%, 10-70% and 4-55% from the fraction < 2 mm, respectively (Table 4). Considering an analysis per region, the ranking obtained for Rfg was $CON^a \approx MN^a \geq BOR^{ab} \geq LUS^b > PAN^c \approx AN^c \approx AC^c \approx NEM^c \approx MS^c$. The ranking for SA was $AN^a \geq MN^{ab} \approx LUS^{ab} \geq NEM^b \geq AC^{bc} \approx MS^{bc} \approx BOR^{bc} \geq PAN^c \approx CON^c$; for SI, the ranking obtained was $CON_a > PAN_b \approx BOR_b \approx AC_b \approx MS_b \geq NEM_{bc} \approx LUS_{bc} \geq MN_c \approx AN_c$; and for CL the resulted ranking was $PAN^a \approx BOR^a \approx MS^a \geq MN^{ab} \approx LUS^{ab} \approx AN^{ab} \approx NEM^{ab} \geq CON^b \approx AC^b$. Regarding comparison between conventional and organic management per region, there were significant differences only at MN region for SA ($t = 4.849$, $P < 0.001$) and SI ($Z = -3.176$, $P < 0.005$), and at CON ($t = -2.313$, $P < 0.05$) and MN ($t = -3.034$, $P < 0.05$) regions for CL. According to the texture triangle from the Natural Resources Conservation Service Soils (USDA), the resulted soil textures across Europe are shown per region in Table 4. Generally, the soil texture was the same at each region independently of the management practices, with the exceptions of BOR, MN, MS and PAN.

Table 3. Soil aggregate size distribution (Agsd) fractionated at different sizes (b: >2000 μm , c: 250-2000 μm ; d: 53-250 μm ; e: <53 μm) and aggregates mean weight diameter (AMWD) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 3																					
Pedoclimatic region	Management	Agsd_b [%]				Agsd_c [%]				Agsd_d [%]				Agsd_e [%]				AMWD [mm]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN												
AC	Conv	4	5	18	1	65	9	76	52	20	10	39	9	10	5	20	2	1.1	0.2	1.5	0.8
	Org	8	6	26	3	23	13	40	6	47	15	75	15	22	18	65	7	0.7	0.3	1.6	0.2
AN	Conv	10	4	19	4	46	10	60	27	33	7	47	24	11	7	28	4	1.1	0.3	1.6	0.6
	Org	6	3	12	2	39	8	56	29	45	9	58	28	10	3	16	6	0.9	0.2	1.2	0.6
BOR	Conv	11	11	33	2	39	10	55	21	29	7	42	19	21	15	50	7	1.1	0.6	2.0	0.3
	Org	14	13	39	2	33	9	50	21	26	11	41	8	27	13	40	8	1.1	0.7	2.4	0.4
CON	Conv	5	6	18	0	22	8	32	10	44	5	54	37	29	7	44	20	0.6	0.3	1.1	0.3
	Org	3	3	10	0	25	11	46	16	42	5	47	32	30	10	46	7	0.5	0.3	1.1	0.3
LUS	Conv	12	9	35	6	47	5	56	37	27	5	33	14	14	4	18	7	1.1	0.2	1.5	0.9
	Org	1	0	1	0	55	12	69	34	30	7	44	21	14	7	30	8	0.7	0.1	0.9	0.5
MN	Conv	28	21	61	4	24	10	38	11	37	10	49	21	11	4	17	5	1.8	1.0	3.3	0.7
	Org	28	20	55	2	16	7	30	8	38	12	59	24	18	9	30	7	1.7	1.0	3.0	0.2
MS	Conv	1	1	2	0	13	5	19	6	53	3	57	46	34	6	43	23	0.3	0.1	0.4	0.2
	Org	9	7	25	2	19	6	32	13	51	7	61	40	20	3	27	17	0.8	0.4	1.5	0.4
NEM	Conv	4	2	9	2	28	11	48	12	54	8	65	41	13	5	23	7	0.6	0.2	1.0	0.3
	Org	6	2	8	3	32	8	46	23	47	8	64	34	15	6	22	4	0.8	0.1	1.0	0.6
PAN	Conv	0	0	1	0	10	5	16	4	57	11	75	46	32	8	41	20	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.2
	Org	1	1	3	0	22	9	41	10	49	8	58	30	28	8	40	19	0.4	0.1	0.6	0.2

Table 4. Rock fragments and gravels (Rfg) and particle size distribution of soil fraction < 2 mm (SA: sand 2-0.05 mm; SI: silt 0.05-0.002 mm; CL: clay <0.002 mm) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Pedoclimatic region — Management		Rfg				SA				SI				CL				Texture
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN													
AC	Conv	6	11	40	1	51	17	73	27	36	18	61	15	12	1	16	11	Sandy clay
	Org	7	8	27	0	52	21	73	23	36	21	65	15	12	2	15	7	
AN	Conv	6	5	19	3	64	5	71	56	23	5	31	15	13	1	14	12	Sandy clay loam
	Org	9	6	20	0	64	3	69	60	23	2	26	19	14	1	14	13	
BOR	Conv	23	13	50	10	45	17	61	9	36	16	70	19	19	5	26	12	Clay loam Clay
	Org	22	12	41	6	41	20	74	13	40	20	68	10	19	5	26	9	
CON	Conv	38	10	58	20	32	11	52	22	55	11	65	35	13	1	13	12	Clay
	Org	33	19	55	3	35	13	60	22	51	13	66	27	14	1	17	12	
LUS	Conv	14	7	31	8	59	4	64	52	27	6	39	20	15	4	17	4	Sandy clay loam
	Org	14	7	31	5	56	14	72	27	29	14	59	11	15	2	19	12	
MN	Conv	38	18	64	10	69	7	76	57	17	7	29	11	14	1	15	13	Sandy loam Sandy clay loam
	Org	24	17	49	3	53	8	65	41	31	7	41	20	16	3	22	13	
MS	Conv	4	1	5	2	49	6	59	41	33	6	41	22	18	3	23	15	Sandy clay loam Sandy clay
	Org	8	4	17	4	47	12	63	24	36	11	55	22	18	2	21	15	
NEM	Conv	5	3	12	2	54	8	67	41	33	10	47	18	13	3	15	4	Sandy clay loam
	Org	7	5	20	4	54	6	61	46	32	6	41	25	14	2	18	10	
PAN	Conv	9	4	15	3	35	11	47	22	42	10	57	23	23	12	55	15	Clay Clay loam
	Org	8	3	11	3	44	16	65	26	38	16	58	20	18	4	27	15	

^a Percentage of the total sample collected; ^b Percentage of the soil fraction < 2 mm; ^c Natural Resources Conservation Service Soils, USDA.

3.1.6 Soil pH in water and in saline solutions

Current acidity, pH_w, and potential acidity (pH in saline solutions), pH_k and pH_c are shown in Table 5 per each European region according to the management practices. Comparing all obtained data, the range for pH_w was between 5.0 and 9.1 while for pH_k and pH_c the ranges were 3.8-8.2 and 3.8-8.1, respectively. It should be noted that all studied regions showed wide representative ranges of soil pHs. The sequence obtained for pH_w was MS^a ≈ MN^a > PAN^b ≈ CON^b > NEM^c ≈ AC^c ≥ AN^{cd} ≥ BOR^d > LUS^e, for pH_k was MS^a ≈ MN^a > PAN^b ≈ CON^b > NEM^c ≈ AC^c ≥ AN^d ≈ BOR^d > LUS^e, and for pH_c was MS^a ≈ MN^a > PAN^b ≥ CON^{bc} ≈ NEM^{bc} ≥ AC^c > AN^d ≈ BOR^d > LUS^e. However, management practices did not result significant differences among overall data for pH_w, pH_k or pH_c. Analyzing management practices per region, only significant differences were found at MN region (t = -3.084, P < 0.05) for pH_w, while for pH_k and for pH_c differences regarding management were found at CON (t = 2.402, P < 0.05), LUS (Z = -2.546, P < 0.05) and MN (t = -5.496, P < 0.001), and at CON (t = 2.242, P < 0.05) and MS (t = 5.178, P < 0.001) regions, respectively.

Table 5. Soil pH in water (pH_w) and in different neutral salt solutions: 1M KCl (pH_{KCl}) and 0.01M CaCl₂ (pH_{CaCl₂}) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 5													
Pedoclimatic region	Management	pH _w				pH _{KCl}				pH _{CaCl₂}			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	7.2	0.6	8.2	5.9	6.4	0.7	7.3	4.9	6.6	0.6	7.5	5.3
	Org	6.9	0.8	8.2	5.9	6.0	1.1	7.4	4.6	6.2	0.8	7.4	5.2
AN	Conv	6.8	0.3	7.4	6.4	5.4	0.3	6.1	5.0	5.9	0.4	6.6	5.5
	Org	6.6	0.3	7.2	6.2	5.6	0.5	6.4	5.0	5.8	0.3	6.6	5.5
BOR	Conv	6.4	0.5	6.9	5.4	5.0	0.4	5.6	4.1	5.5	0.4	6.1	4.6
	Org	6.5	0.4	7.0	5.7	5.3	0.6	6.2	4.6	5.8	0.4	6.2	5.1
CON	Conv	7.9	0.3	8.2	7.3	7.2	0.3	7.7	6.9	7.2	0.3	7.6	6.5
	Org	7.6	0.6	8.4	6.7	6.7	0.7	7.6	5.6	6.7	0.6	7.4	5.7
LUS	Conv	5.5	0.3	5.9	5.1	4.1	0.3	4.7	3.8	4.1	0.2	4.5	3.8
	Org	5.4	0.2	5.7	5.0	4.3	0.1	4.5	4.1	4.2	0.2	4.5	3.8
MN	Conv	8.5	0.4	9.1	8.1	7.8	0.2	8.0	7.4	7.9	0.1	8.0	7.6
	Org	8.8	0.1	8.9	8.7	8.1	0.0	8.1	8.1	7.9	0.0	8.0	7.8
MS	Conv	8.6	0.2	8.9	8.2	8.0	0.1	8.2	7.9	8.0	0.1	8.1	7.9
	Org	8.8	0.2	9.0	8.4	8.0	0.1	8.2	7.9	7.9	0.0	7.9	7.8
NEM	Conv	7.1	0.7	8.1	6.1	6.0	0.9	7.2	4.8	6.3	0.7	7.3	5.0
	Org	7.1	0.4	7.8	6.7	6.1	0.6	7.0	5.4	6.6	0.6	7.6	5.9
PAN	Conv	8.2	0.4	8.6	7.4	7.3	0.6	7.8	6.2	7.2	0.4	7.6	6.4
	Org	7.9	0.6	8.4	6.3	6.9	0.8	7.4	4.9	6.9	0.7	7.5	5.2

3.1.7 Cation exchange capacity (CEC), Base saturation (Bs) and Electrical conductivity (EC)

CEC and Bs are shown in Table 6 classified by region and management practices. Comparing all obtained data, CEC ranged between 4.5 and 42 cmol/kg and Bs ranged between 14 and 100%. Analyzed per region, the ranking obtained for CEC and Bs were $PAN^a \geq BOR^{ab} \approx AC^{ab} \approx NEM^{ab} \geq MS^b \approx AN^b \approx CON^b \approx MN^b \approx LUS^b$ and $MN^a \approx MS^a \approx PAN^a \approx CON^a > AC^b \approx NEM^b \approx BOR^b \approx AN^b > LUS^c$, respectively. Management practices did not show significant differences among overall data. Comparing management practices at each region, differences were found for CEC at LUS ($t = -4.854$, $P < 0.001$) and MN ($Z = -2.041$, $P < 0.05$) regions, while for Bs, any region showed significant differences between conventional and organic management.

Table 6. Effective cation exchange capacity (CEC), base saturation (Bs) and electrical conductivity (EC) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 6													
Pedoclimatic region	Management	CEC [cmol/kg]				Bs [%]				EC [dS/m]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	16	6	30	9	85	24	100	44	0.05	0.02	0.08	0.01
	Org	18	7	31	8	70	28	100	31	0.06	0.03	0.10	0.01
AN	Conv	16	9	42	8	66	23	100	24	0.11	0.03	0.18	0.08
	Org	15	4	26	11	65	19	100	28	0.11	0.04	0.16	0.04
BOR	Conv	21	8	39	10	67	14	86	42	0.07	0.02	0.10	0.04
	Org	20	2	24	17	73	5	81	66	0.07	0.03	0.11	0.02
CON	Conv	14	6	22	6	100	0	100	100	0.03	0.01	0.05	0.02
	Org	16	6	24	6	93	12	100	72	0.04	0.02	0.07	0.02
LUS	Conv	10	2	14	6	31	11	49	14	0.04	0.02	0.07	0.02
	Org	16	3	21	10	25	7	45	18	0.09	0.05	0.15	0.02
MN	Conv	16	2	20	13	100	0	100	100	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.01
	Org	14	1	16	12	100	0	100	100	0.05	0.01	0.06	0.02
MS	Conv	16	3	21	12	100	0	100	100	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01
	Org	16	3	21	11	100	0	100	100	0.05	0.02	0.08	0.02
NEM	Conv	15	5	19	4	65	31	100	33	0.08	0.05	0.18	0.04
	Org	18	9	38	7	84	22	100	39	0.08	0.03	0.13	0.05
PAN	Conv	23	6	31	15	100	0	100	100	0.08	0.03	0.11	0.02
	Org	23	8	35	14	98	8	100	76	0.12	0.04	0.20	0.08

Electrical conductivity is indicative of the amount of salts in soil, i.e., it is an indirect measure which provides information about soil salinity. EC ranged between 0.01 and 0.2 dS/m among all soils. Average, maximum and minimum values per region and management are shown in Table 6. Analyzing per region, the resulted ranking was $AN^a \geq PAN^{ab} \approx NEM^{ab} \geq BOR^b \approx LUS^b \approx AC^b > CON^c \approx MS^c \approx MN^c$. Additionally, management practices also result in significant differences overall EC ($Z = -3.015$, $P < 0.005$) showing average values of 0.058 dS/m in conventional and 0.075 dS/m in organic management. Analyzing each region separately, management practices showed significant differences at LUS ($t = -3.469$, $P < 0.005$), MN ($t = -3.841$, $P < 0.005$), MS ($t = -3.513$, $P < 0.005$) and PAN ($Z = -2.449$, $P < 0.05$) regions for EC.

3.1.8 Organic matter content (OM), Total organic carbon (TOC), Particulate organic carbon (POC) and Carbonates content ($CaCO_3$)

Organic matter ranged between 1.6 and 19.1% among all studied soils. Average, maximum and minimum values per region and management are shown in Table 7. Comparing data per region resulted in the following ranking: $BOR^a \geq LUS^{ab} \approx NEM^{ab} \approx PAN^{ab} \geq AN^b \approx CON^b \approx AC^b > MN^c \approx MS^c$. Analyzing management practices, significant differences were found between conventional and organic management only at LUS ($Z = -2.481$, $P < 0.05$) and MN ($t = 4.338$, $P < 0.001$) regions.

Total organic carbon was found between 4.6 and 103 g/kg among all studied European soils. Data regarding average, maximum and minimum at each region and considering the management practices are shown in Table 7. Data analyzed per region showed a ranking as follows: $BOR^a \geq LUS^{ab} \approx NEM^{ab} \approx PAN^{ab} \approx AN^{ab} \geq CON^b \approx AC^b > MN^c \approx MS^c$. In addition, management also led to significant differences among overall TOC ($t = -1.994$, $P < 0.05$) showing average values of 17.3 g/kg in conventional and 20.5 g/kg in organic management. Considering data per region, management practices were only significantly different at LUS ($t = -3.059$, $P < 0.01$) and MN ($Z = -3.1$, $P < 0.005$) regions.

Particulate organic carbon ranged between 0.8 and 74 g/kg among all samples. Results from each region and management are shown in Table 7. Comparing all data per region, the resulted ranking is $BOR^a \approx LUS^a \geq NEM^{ab} \approx AN^{ab} \approx PAN^{ab} \geq AC^b \approx CON^b \geq MN^{bc} \geq MS^c$. However, management practices did not provide significant differences overall data. Analyzing data per region, management practices showed significant differences at LUS ($Z = -2.667$, $P < 0.01$), MN ($t = 2.295$, $P < 0.05$) and MS ($t = -2.31$, $P < 0.05$)

Carbonates content ($CaCO_3$): carbonates content ranged between 0.6 and 88% among all studied soils. Carbonates data obtained from analyzed soils are shown in Table 7 taken into account each region and management practices. Analyzing all data per region, the ranking obtained is $MS^a \approx MN^a > PAN^b \geq AC^{ab} \approx CON^{bc} \approx BOR^{bc} \approx NEM^{bc} \approx AN^{bc} \geq LUS^c$. However, the factor of management did not provide significant differences among all carbonates. Considering

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management practices per region, there were significant differences between conventional and organic at LUS ($t = -2.263$, $P < 0.05$), MN ($t = -3.59$, $P < 0.005$), MS ($t = -4.688$, $P < 0.005$).

Table 7. Soil organic matter (OM), total organic carbon (TOC), particulate organic carbon (POC) and carbonates (CaCO₃) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 7																	
Pedoclimatic region	Management	OM [%]				TOC [g/kg]				POC [g/kg]				CaCO ₃ [%]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	3.1	0.7	5.0	2.4	14.3	3.2	20.7	9.7	5.1	2.3	11.9	2.2	2.6	2.6	10.4	0.8
	Org	3.6	0.8	5.7	2.6	17.3	4.3	26.5	11.3	5.8	2.5	12.6	2.5	2.8	2.9	9.8	0.8
AN	Conv	4.1	0.9	5.6	2.9	17.9	4.6	25.7	12.5	7.1	4.3	13.8	2.7	2.0	2.3	8.2	0.7
	Org	3.9	1.2	5.8	2.0	17.6	5.7	26.3	8.5	7.6	5.6	18.6	1.9	0.9	0.3	1.5	0.6
BOR	Conv	6.5	1.6	10.3	5.2	30.6	8.3	49.4	22.2	18.1	8.6	34.5	10.7	1.8	0.5	2.6	1.0
	Org	7.1	4.3	19.1	4.1	33.6	25.2	103.3	19.2	18.2	20.1	74.0	6.9	1.8	0.4	2.5	1.2
CON	Conv	4.0	0.9	5.0	2.3	16.6	4.8	21.7	9.5	5.1	2.2	8.4	2.6	3.2	1.9	7.5	1.0
	Org	3.7	1.1	4.8	1.6	15.9	4.4	20.4	7.6	4.3	2.1	8.4	2.4	2.1	1.5	5.3	0.8
LUS	Conv	4.1	1.4	7.1	3.1	17.7	5.9	29.6	12.7	8.3	4.3	16.3	4.2	1.2	0.2	1.5	0.9
	Org	7.2	3.0	13.3	2.9	32.1	15.6	66.1	11.9	16.9	9.3	39.8	5.5	1.6	0.6	3.2	1.0
MN	Conv	3.0	0.3	3.5	2.5	12.4	1.6	14.1	9.6	4.5	1.1	5.9	2.8	33.3	20.8	67.8	2.1
	Org	2.4	0.3	2.9	2.0	9.2	1.2	10.5	6.4	3.1	1.5	5.7	1.3	60.7	12.2	75.8	42.4
MS	Conv	2.3	0.4	2.8	1.6	8.2	2.0	10.4	4.6	2.1	0.8	3.3	0.8	51.9	3.1	57.1	47.3
	Org	2.3	0.5	3.4	1.8	9.0	2.2	13.2	6.1	3.0	1.0	4.3	1.7	68.4	10.7	88.5	56.6
NEM	Conv	4.6	1.4	7.0	2.8	20.8	7.3	35.6	11.9	6.7	2.4	10.1	3.0	1.6	1.4	4.7	0.6
	Org	5.8	2.1	9.1	3.1	26.9	10.4	43.1	11.2	9.7	6.4	22.4	2.8	1.9	1.1	4.2	0.7
PAN	Conv	4.1	0.8	5.3	2.9	17.7	4.6	25.2	10.0	5.3	2.2	9.0	1.6	8.0	7.5	21.7	1.1
	Org	4.4	2.0	9.2	2.9	20.4	10.2	42.7	11.0	9.2	10.5	33.1	2.1	4.4	3.5	9.9	0.9

3.1.9 Soil total nitrogen and nitrogen forms

Total nitrogen (Nt) and nitrogen forms, i.e., ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrates (NO_3^-) and nitrites (NO_2^-) ranged between 0.5-7.1 g/kg, 1.1-9.8 mg/kg, 17.4-188.2 mg/kg and non detectable till 11.8 mg/kg, respectively among all studied soil samples. All data segmented by region and management are shown in Table 8. Analyzing all data per region independently of soil management practices, the resulted rankings are: $\text{BOR}^a \geq \text{LUS}^{ab} \approx \text{NEM}^{ab} \approx \text{PAN}^{ab} \geq \text{AN}^b \approx \text{CON}^b \approx \text{AC}^b > \text{MS}^c \approx \text{MN}^c$ for total nitrogen, $\text{PAN}^a \geq \text{LUS}^{ab} \approx \text{BOR}^{ab} \approx \text{MS}^{ab} \approx \text{MN}^{ab} \approx \text{NEM}^{ab} \approx \text{AN}^{ab} \geq \text{AC}^b \approx \text{CON}^b$ for ammonium, $\text{AN}^a \approx \text{BOR}^a \approx \text{NEM}^a \approx \text{AC}^a \geq \text{MN}^{ab} \approx \text{LUS}^{ab} \geq \text{MS}^b \approx \text{CON}^b \approx \text{PAN}^b$ for nitrates, and $\text{BOR}^a \geq \text{MN}^{ab} \approx \text{AC}^{ab} \approx \text{AN}^{ab} \approx \text{MS}^{ab} \geq \text{NEM}^b \approx \text{CON}^b \approx \text{PAN}^b > \text{LUS}^c$ for nitrites. Additionally, management practices showed significant differences among overall Nt ($t = -2.435$, $P < 0.05$), ammonium ($Z = -2.067$, $P < 0.05$) and nitrates ($t = 2.562$, $P < 0.05$), resulting in average lower values in conventional management (1.7 g/kg) versus organic (2.0 g/kg) for Nt and for ammonium (3.1 and 3.4 mg/kg in conventional and organic, respectively) while for nitrates, average values were higher in conventional (78.5 mg/kg) versus organic (67.5 mg/kg) management among overall data. Performing analysis per region where management practices were compared, significant differences were found for total nitrogen at AC ($t = -3.049$, $P < 0.01$), LUS ($t = -3.336$, $P < 0.01$) and MN ($t = 3.881$, $P < 0.005$) regions, for ammonium at LUS ($P < 0.05$), MS ($t = -2.849$, $P < 0.05$) and PAN ($t = 2.769$, $P < 0.05$) regions, for nitrates at AC ($t = 2.735$, $P < 0.05$), CON ($t = -2.444$, $P < 0.05$), LUS ($t = -3.116$, $P < 0.01$), MN ($t = 3.239$, $P < 0.01$) and PAN ($P < 0.05$) regions, and for nitrites at MN ($Z = -3.099$, $P < 0.005$) and PAN ($Z = -2.42$, $P < 0.05$) regions.

3.1.10 Macronutrients

Available phosphorus (Pav) and exchangeable K, Ca, and Mg ranged between 4-263 mg/kg, 53-1115 mg/kg, 231-6098 mg/kg, 23-752 mg/kg and 8-807 mg/kg, respectively, among all studied soil samples. Considering the content per region, the resulted rankings are as follows: $\text{LUS}^a > \text{AC}^b \geq \text{PAN}^{bc} \geq \text{BOR}^c \approx \text{CON}^c \approx \text{AN}^c \geq \text{NEM}^{cd} \approx \text{MN}^{cd} \geq \text{MS}^d$ for Pav, $\text{CON}^a \approx \text{MS}^a \approx \text{AC}^a \geq \text{PAN}^{ab} \approx \text{LUS}^{ab} \approx \text{BOR}^{ab} \approx \text{AN}^{ab} \geq \text{MN}^b \approx \text{NEM}^b$ for Kex, $\text{PAN}^a > \text{MN}^b \approx \text{CON}^b \approx \text{MS}^b \geq \text{BOR}^{bc} \approx \text{AC}^{bc} \approx \text{NEM}^{bc} \geq \text{AN}^c > \text{LUS}^d$ for Caex, and $\text{MS}^a \approx \text{BOR}^a \approx \text{PAN}^a > \text{MN}^b \approx \text{AC}^b \approx \text{NEM}^b \approx \text{CON}^b > \text{AN}^c \approx \text{LUS}^c$ for Mgex. All resulted data per region taken into account the management practices are shown in Table 9. In addition, management factor also led to significant differences among overall data for Pav ($Z = -2.296$, $P < 0.05$) with higher average values in conventional (54.6 mg/kg) than in organic (43.3 mg/g) management and for Mgex ($Z = -1.973$, $P < 0.05$) with lower average values for conventional (179 mg/kg) than for organic management (205 mg/kg). Those data were analyzed to determine the influence of management practices per region and significant differences were found at LUS ($Z = -2.667$, $P < 0.01$), MN ($Z = -3.02$, $P < 0.005$), MS ($t = 2.644$, $P < 0.05$) and NEM ($t = 3.246$, $P < 0.01$) regions for available P, at AN ($t = -2.566$, $P < 0.05$) and NEM ($t = 2.307$, $P < 0.05$) for Kex, at LUS ($t = -2.932$, $P < 0.01$), MS ($t = 2.64$, $P < 0.05$) and NEM ($P < 0.05$) for Caex, and at AN ($t = -2.191$, $P < 0.05$), LUS ($Z = -2.605$, $P < 0.01$) and NEM ($t = -3.637$, $P < 0.01$) for Mgex.

Table 8. Soil total Nitrogen (Nt) and Nitrogen-forms: ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrates (NO₃⁻) and nitrites (NO₂⁻) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 8																	
Pedoclimatic region	Management	Nt [g/kg]				NH ₄ ⁺ [mg/kg]				NO ₃ ⁻ [mg/kg]				NO ₂ ⁻ [mg/kg]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	1.4	0.3	2.1	1.1	2.3	1.0	4.1	1.3	95.3	24.2	139.9	44.1	8.2	2.2	11.8	3.1
	Org	1.8	0.3	2.3	1.3	3.1	2.0	8.1	1.1	67.9	25.8	108.4	34.3	7.0	3.0	11.7	3.5
AN	Conv	1.8	0.3	2.3	1.3	2.9	1.5	6.9	1.9	108.2	36.1	188.2	71.7	8.9	2.7	10.9	3.3
	Org	1.8	0.5	2.6	1.0	3.5	1.3	5.2	2.1	83.1	18.9	108.9	43.7	8.7	2.2	10.4	3.7
BOR	Conv	2.7	0.5	3.7	2.1	3.0	1.0	5.4	2.1	96.5	20.6	125.3	48.4	9.8	1.8	11.7	5.0
	Org	2.8	1.5	7.1	2.0	3.9	1.5	6.5	1.8	83.8	24.1	112.7	38.9	8.3	2.8	10.8	4.0
CON	Conv	1.7	0.5	2.3	1.0	2.1	0.7	3.2	1.2	62.7	20.2	91.8	32.4	2.9	0.1	3.1	2.6
	Org	1.5	0.4	2.0	0.7	1.6	0.7	3.5	1.1	45.7	8.8	60.0	34.0	2.9	0.2	3.2	2.6
LUS	Conv	1.6	0.4	2.4	1.2	3.3	2.6	9.8	1.7	56.4	16.4	94.2	37.8	<DL	<DL	<DL	<DL
	Org	2.8	1.3	5.2	1.1	4.0	1.5	6.2	1.9	86.4	29.3	138.4	48.1	<DL	<DL	<DL	<DL
MN	Conv	1.1	0.2	1.3	0.7	3.3	0.8	5.2	2.4	90.4	17.5	124.3	70.5	9.2	0.5	10.5	8.8
	Org	0.8	0.2	1.2	0.6	3.2	0.4	3.9	2.3	69.0	11.4	97.4	60.1	7.9	0.4	8.7	7.4
MS	Conv	1.1	0.3	1.4	0.5	2.9	0.6	4.3	2.3	61.0	24.3	101.9	30.9	6.3	2.3	8.5	3.2
	Org	1.3	0.2	1.6	1.0	3.8	0.8	5.1	2.6	53.3	19.8	77.8	27.8	6.2	2.3	8.3	3.1
NEM	Conv	1.8	0.5	2.8	1.1	3.1	0.5	4.1	2.5	83.0	28.3	141.5	50.8	6.3	2.6	9.1	3.2
	Org	2.5	1.1	4.4	1.2	3.4	0.3	4.0	2.9	83.7	30.1	139.5	40.5	7.0	3.2	11.5	3.6
PAN	Conv	1.8	0.4	2.4	1.1	5.4	1.7	8.2	3.4	48.3	27.8	117.5	24.5	1.8	0.3	2.3	1.4
	Org	2.1	1.0	4.3	1.2	3.6	1.0	5.8	2.3	28.6	10.2	45.6	17.4	2.8	1.1	5.0	1.6

<DL: below detection limit

Table 9. Soil macronutrients: available P (Pav) and exchangeable K, Ca, Mg and Na (Kex, Caex, Mgex and Naex, respectively) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 9																					
Pedoclimatic region	Management	Pav [mg/kg]				Kex [mg/kg]				Caex [mg/kg]				Mgex [mg/kg]				Naex [mg/kg]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	63	26	108	19	268	95	410	118	2092	1266	5534	695	178	94	478	112	93	35	151	19
	Org	65	21	92	28	283	148	569	77	2083	1338	4243	545	156	54	268	75	62	30	109	19
AN	Conv	41	9	53	18	138	41	201	87	1634	366	2292	962	78	15	101	56	54	21	101	38
	Org	33	10	44	18	214	85	372	136	1534	338	1977	1114	101	30	154	55	62	22	101	37
BOR	Conv	41	14	72	26	182	62	296	99	2163	1102	4035	1072	314	224	752	95	46	22	80	16
	Org	41	15	67	21	188	83	293	93	2204	325	2696	1608	318	105	473	215	73	49	172	29
CON	Conv	38	7	47	25	310	121	573	184	2360	931	3702	990	155	77	241	54	118	67	227	26
	Org	41	28	114	17	393	312	1105	70	2595	1177	4245	714	149	53	202	58	55	44	146	18
LUS	Conv	180	70	263	49	260	72	430	182	345	103	589	231	49	33	137	23	32	17	78	20
	Org	88	56	188	11	204	157	632	65	500	140	796	329	77	27	122	36	47	15	86	31
MN	Conv	39	36	116	10	164	80	356	96	2706	532	3770	2246	193	95	367	111	45	24	99	16
	Org	10	0	11	10	160	49	238	79	2424	177	2645	2157	150	67	295	59	35	13	57	18
MS	Conv	22	13	45	11	284	116	459	118	2486	303	2871	2111	255	136	524	84	122	154	521	20
	Org	11	2	18	10	354	142	554	165	2106	339	2682	1566	385	142	582	238	302	221	807	57
NEM	Conv	41	23	85	16	173	85	367	62	1498	931	3201	706	88	29	131	56	22	8	38	15
	Org	17	7	34	10	103	45	181	53	2491	1231	4806	1158	246	134	491	76	22	8	35	11
PAN	Conv	24	13	49	4	221	97	392	82	3896	858	5018	2582	304	192	664	131	30	36	130	8
	Org	66	82	245	10	242	174	559	62	3701	1292	6098	2154	312	130	574	177	47	60	214	16

3.1.11 Micronutrients

Bioavailable Cu, Zn, Fe and Mn (Cuba, Znba, Feba and Mnba, respectively) ranged between 0.1-50 mg/kg, 0.1-65 mg/kg, 1.3-346 mg/kg and 2.2-83 mg/kg, respectively for all analyzed soil samples independently of region and management. Considering the factor of region, the ranking of the results obtained is $PAN^a \approx AC^a \geq BOR^{ab} \approx LUS^{ab} \geq CON^b \geq AN^{bc} \geq MS^c \approx MN^c \approx NEM^c$ for Cuba, $CON^a > AC^b \geq LUS^{bc} \geq PAN^c \approx AN^c \approx NEM^c \approx BOR^c \approx MN^c \approx MS^c$ for Znba, $BOR^a > AC^b \geq LUS^{bc} \geq NEM^c > AN^d \geq CON^{de} \geq PAN^e > MN^f \approx MS^f$ for Feba and, $AN^a \approx PAN^a \approx CON^a \approx LUS^{ab} \geq NEM^{ab} \approx AC^b \approx BOR^b \approx MN^b \approx MS^b$ for Mnba. The factor of management practices did not cause significant changes among micronutrients. All data per region taken into account the management practices are shown in Table 10. Analyzing management practices per region, only at LUS ($Z = -1.987$, $P < 0.05$) were found significant differences between conventional and organic management for Cuba, at CON ($t = 2.274$, $P < 0.05$) and LUS ($Z = -2.047$, $P < 0.05$) for Znba, at LUS ($Z = -2.171$, $P < 0.05$), MN ($Z = -2.721$, $P < 0.01$), MS ($t = 2.64$, $P < 0.05$), NEM ($t = -2.183$, $P < 0.05$) and PAN ($t = -3.52$, $P < 0.01$) for Feba, while for Mnba any significant differences were found between different management practices at any region.

Table 10. Soil micronutrients: bioavailable Cu, Zn, Fe and Mg (Cuba, Znba, Feba and Mnba, respectively) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 10																	
Pedoclimatic region	Management	Cuba [mg/kg]				Znba [mg/kg]				Feba [mg/kg]				Mnba [mg/kg]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	2.8	1.6	7.1	1.2	6.0	3.0	12.6	1.7	68.9	26.9	123.6	26.9	7.9	4.7	17.2	2.2
	Org	2.0	0.4	2.8	1.2	6.4	3.2	11.2	1.3	103.0	58.4	232.1	41.8	7.9	7.1	24.1	2.5
AN	Conv	1.4	0.5	2.5	0.9	2.1	1.4	4.8	0.9	49.8	17.5	78.9	31.3	21.4	9.5	38.9	6.6
	Org	1.1	0.5	2.1	0.5	1.6	0.6	3.0	1.0	41.1	15.0	75.8	24.3	25.9	13.3	60.1	10.4
BOR	Conv	2.0	1.0	4.1	1.0	1.4	1.6	5.5	0.3	190.0	85.9	345.9	96.9	7.4	5.1	20.0	2.4
	Org	1.6	0.9	3.5	0.5	1.0	0.6	2.3	0.5	135.7	81.8	291.3	50.0	8.3	4.1	15.1	3.6
CON	Conv	1.2	0.4	1.6	0.6	28.9	17.4	64.9	6.6	28.6	11.7	53.0	11.6	16.9	4.1	25.6	12.0
	Org	1.4	0.5	2.2	0.6	14.7	9.3	35.2	2.8	40.8	18.6	83.7	20.6	18.0	9.5	38.4	7.9
LUS	Conv	1.6	0.7	3.0	1.0	5.0	4.3	16.6	1.6	102.0	54.3	239.7	47.6	12.6	5.9	24.3	5.0
	Org	1.7	2.8	10.8	0.4	2.6	2.5	9.0	0.4	63.9	45.7	152.3	21.8	15.9	13.5	46.0	3.2
MN	Conv	0.7	0.7	2.2	0.2	1.0	1.3	4.4	0.2	4.7	2.5	11.0	2.1	7.5	2.1	11.5	4.9
	Org	0.7	0.3	1.3	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.7	0.2	2.5	1.0	4.7	1.3	6.9	2.0	10.0	3.9
MS	Conv	1.0	0.3	1.5	0.7	0.6	0.3	1.1	0.3	3.2	0.7	4.1	2.2	6.5	1.7	8.9	4.1
	Org	0.8	0.4	1.8	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.7	0.2	3.1	1.0	5.2	1.8	6.8	3.2	12.2	3.1
NEM	Conv	0.4	0.2	0.7	0.1	1.6	1.3	4.0	0.3	40.2	11.5	58.2	23.3	9.4	6.1	22.1	2.8
	Org	0.5	0.3	1.1	0.2	0.9	0.3	1.3	0.4	55.5	18.9	87.7	25.0	11.3	5.7	22.2	5.3
PAN	Conv	6.3	15.3	49.9	0.7	0.8	0.6	2.5	0.1	11.0	5.1	23.4	6.5	21.5	7.7	36.7	12.5
	Org	2.2	0.7	3.2	1.3	3.8	4.6	15.4	0.4	38.8	24.4	87.0	6.0	24.9	22.9	82.7	6.7

3.1.12 Pesticide residues in soils

A total of 617 pesticide residues have been analyzed in the studied soil samples, 78 were detected. At least one compound was found in 152 soil samples (80% of studied soils), both organically and conventionally managed soils from all regions sampled (Table 11). Glyphosate and its by-product, AMPA, were detected in all regions except for conventionally managed soils in the MS region (Table 11). In other regions such as AC, CON, MN or NEM for organic and PAN conventionally managed, only one sample showed one of these compounds. Glufosinate ammonium and metabolites (n-Acetyl-glufosinate and MPP) were not detected.

In general, organically managed soils showed lower amounts of total pesticides (0.05 mg/kg vs 0.19 mg/kg, respectively) and detected compounds (60 vs 92) compared to conventional ones. The sequence of regions obtained concerning the sum of different pesticides concentrations, excluding glyphosate related compounds, was $CON^a > AN^b \approx AC^b \geq MS^{bc} \approx NEM^{bc} \approx LUS^{bc} \approx BOR^{bc} \approx PAN^{bc} \geq MN^c$, while for the sum of glyphosate and AMPA it was $BOR^a \geq NEM^{ab} \approx LUS^{ab} \approx CON^{ab} \approx AN^{ab} \approx MN^{ab} \approx PAN^{ab} \approx MS^{ab} \geq AC^b$. The factor management showed significant differences for the sum of all analyzed compounds ($t=6.404, p < 0.01$) and the sum of all analyzed compounds excluding glyphosate and their metabolites ($t=4.964, p < 0.01$) between organic and conventional wheat field soils. However, no significant differences between managements were found for glyphosate ($t=1.492, p > 0.05$) and AMPA ($t=1.492, p > 0.05$).

The Fenbutatin oxide, an organotin pesticide used as an acaricide in the control of mites, in particular spider mites, was the most detected in conventional (21.8 % of soil samples) and organic (18.70 %) agricultural management (Figure 2), followed by the glyphosate herbicide metabolite AMPA (21.8% for conventional and 9.57% for organic managed soils). Although in different proportions, glyphosate, Boscalid, Diflufenican, Tebuconazole, p,p'-DDE and Dinoterb were the most detected in both agricultural managements.

Figure 2. Ten most detected compounds for each conventional (a) and agricultural management (b).

Table 11. Soil pesticides (Glyphosate+ampra and multi-pesticides) at sampling time in wheat crops from the studied pedoclimatic regions under conventional and organic management.

Table 11									
Pedoclimatic region	Management	$\Sigma_{\text{Gly+AMPA}}$ [mg/kg]				$\Sigma_{\text{multi-pesticides}}$ [mg/kg]			
		avrg	SD	MAX	MIN	avrg	SD	MAX	MIN
AC	Conv	0.06	0.04	0.10	0.01	0.23	0.11	0.43	0.02
	Org	0.01	-	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.22	0.01
AN	Conv	0.07	0.05	0.15	0.01	0.24	0.10	0.45	0.14
	Org	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.08	0.09	0.21	0.01
BOR	Conv	0.12	0.07	0.23	0.04	0.07	0.08	0.25	0.01
	Org	0.05	0.03	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01
CON	Conv	0.06	0.07	0.11	0.02	0.46	0.21	0.97	0.23
	Org	0.01	-	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.13	0.41	0.01
LUS	Conv	0.07	0.04	0.13	0.02	0.08	0.05	0.18	0.01
	Org	0.06	0.06	0.13	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.08	0.02
MN	Conv	0.04	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.11	0.01
	Org	0.01	-	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01
MS	Conv	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.17	0.12	0.43	0.02
	Org	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.06	0.12	0.34	0.01
NEM	Conv	0.09	0.04	0.13	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.20	0.01
	Org	0.01	-	0.01	0.01	0.01	-	0.01	0.01
PAN	Conv	0.04	-	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.17	0.01
	Org	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.01

n.d. Not detected.

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4 Conclusions

The soils sampled for WP3 in 9 pedoclimatic regions cover a wide range of variation in their characteristics. As examples, pH ranged between 5.0 and 9.2, organic matter between 1.5 and 19% and clay content between 5 and 55%. Generally there is an important effect of pedoclimatic region on soil characteristics. However, the effect of type of management (conventional vs organic) presents a no clear effect on soil characteristics. The high variation found in soil characteristics, together with high variation in climatic conditions between sampling areas will help to elucidate how soil organisms' development and activity depends on the condition and composition of their environment.

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